

Review of Key Management Mechanisms

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In this report, we present the results of a literature review of the mechanisms used for key and identity management. The implications of this review are reflected in [6]. The review was conducted with the purpose of identifying how to secure keys related to the Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) based certificates. The assumption made before the literature review was that to eliminate a single point of failure, some sort of decentralisation is needed for control over the digital identity.

Search Strategy. For the literature review, we use the following keywords and their combinations: “key management”, “user”, “PKI”, “identity”, “distributed”. The search of literature was performed in Scopus and Google Scholar databases. Additionally, the forward and backward snowballing was used based on the found papers.

Data extraction. The initial set of selected papers for the review included 34 papers, while 17 were selected for data extraction. The data has been extracted based on the relevance to problem scope and existence of evaluation of the mechanism for securing keys. The mechanisms for key management and the identity management system characteristics were the data extracted from the selected papers.

1 Targeted System Characteristics

To study the security of Organisational Digital Identity (ODI) ¹, we consider characteristics targeted by the key and identity management mechanisms. The need for the characteristics depends on the scenario and business needs. Based on the literature review, we gather a set of non-functional characteristics which affect the security of Identity Management (IdM) systems. The characteristics are evaluated in Section 2.

1.1 Business goals-oriented

From the business perspective, the following characteristics, mostly reflecting the trust of business in entities, may be targeted. *Trustlessness* is a part of the Zero Trust (ZT) architecture [24] and refers to the ability of the system

¹If not specified otherwise, we also use *identity* to refer to ODI.

to operate without relying on the honest behaviour of internal or external entity [19]. To react to the dishonest behaviour, the IdM system may target to deliver *traceability* that refers to the ability to know who did what, when, and how [14, 9]. The more proactive approach to secure the system against internal attacks is *privilege escalation prevention*, which aims to restrict users from gaining unauthorised access to higher levels of privilege, ensuring that users only have access to the resources and actions they are explicitly authorised to use. In this research, we consider privilege escalation as a result of both privilege escalation attacks and privilege misuse. One more way of enabling zero trust is *decentralisation*, which refers to distributing the responsibility for managing ODI and its keys across multiple entities to enhance security, resilience, and user control. If possible, differentiating between *multiple users* contributes to better security in the decentralised setting. Another aspect of the system’s security that is important for business is its availability, which defines the ability of the organisation to deliver its value using the system. *System availability* [14] is crucial to be enabled both in the normal condition of everyday data exchange and in case of extraordinary trigger events (e.g. when the involved in the ODI management employee leaves an organisation or when the access to system component with keys is lost). Thus, securing ODI includes the ability of the system to withstand failures (i.e. *fault tolerance*) [14, 3]. and to adjust based on the failures’ outcomes [19] (i.e. *resilience*). Also, regaining access to the private keys in case they are lost or compromised (i.e. *recoverability*) supports availability and ODI security. Finally, the *usability* of the ODI refers to the feasibility to manage identity and key, including convenience. ODI usability defines whether an organisation is able to use the proposed ODI in the existing infrastructure. Besides, the usability defines whether the end-users will use the ODI following the defined interaction set-up with ODI or they will try to avoid the security measures [14, 26, 19].

1.2 Cryptography-oriented

From the cryptographic perspective, the primary means for achieving authenticity and integrity of data are digital signatures. The following are the classical targeted characteristics. *Unforgeability* ensures that a valid signature cannot be created by a non-authorised entity without having access to the private key [9, 27]. Assuming the private key has not been compromised a digital signature provides *non-repudiation* – the holder of the private key cannot deny the origin of a valid signature. For common signing schemes, such as the Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm (ECDSA [15]) or Rivest-Shamir-Adleman (RSA), the signatures signed with the same private key are linked together through the single public key that verifies them. Such *linkability* of signatures or keys determines whether two or more signatures or public keys are coming from the same identity [13, 9]. The possibility to link different signatures may or may not be desired. Thereby, unforgeability, non-repudiation and linkability contribute to the authenticity and integrity of the exchanged data.

2 Review of mechanisms supporting ODI

According to NIST SP 800-57 [8], the cryptographic key management lifecycle consists of four phases: pre-operational, operational, post-operational and destroyed. Identity management pre includes three key management functions: (i) generation and distribution of asymmetric key pairs for the key generation during the pre-operational phase; (ii) the key registration (e.g. the certification by a PKI CA) during the pre-operational phase; and (iii) storage, usage and back up of keys during the operational phase. Fig. 1 depict key parameters and artefacts used within a key management cycle. The certification is crucial for establishing trust within the system as it enables verification of the exchanged data integrity. Our research aims to comply with the existing verification process to remain IdM backwards compatible. Thus, we exclude the second stage from our analysis. In this section, we provide an overview of the cryptographic and non-cryptographic mechanisms identified through the literature review.

Figure 1: Key management phases: key functions, parameters and artefacts.

We focus on the cryptographic schemes that provide digital signatures because our main concerns are the integrity and authenticity (origin) of the exchange data. Therefore, *key* in the following text refers to an asymmetric key, more precisely a keypair, if not stated otherwise. Whether we talk about the key pair or the individual private or public key should be clear from the context.

2.1 Pre-operational key phase

Depending on the signing scheme, the *key* – in particular its private and public part – has a different (mostly mathematical) *structure*. No matter the scheme there are values that need to be generated randomly (e.g. the prime numbers in RSA or private scalars in ECDSA). Those random values are obtained, ideally, from a truly random number generator (TRNG) or a pseudo-random number generator (PRNGs) that is *seeded*² by TRNG. However, the seed can also be derived from a user provided input such as a password or a passphrase. While

²Instantiated with a particular value called seed.

Password-Based Key Derivation Functions (e.g. PBKDF2 or Argon2) are commonly used for deriving symmetric keys (e.g. for AES) their result can also be used for seeding a PRNG and deriving asymmetric keys. In practice, such keys are likely only as secure as the password itself due to the generally low entropy of passwords. The Multi-Factor Key Derivation Function (MFKDF) [19] combines many factors³ and therefore greatly improves the security of the derived key. Depending on the desired end setup, the factors may or may not be all controlled by a single party. Next, there are protocols for *distributed key generation* (DKG) such as FROST (which is based on elliptic curves) [18]. In DKG, multiple parties interact in a protocol and end up with individual secret shares of a key. This key can later be used for (threshold) signing.

Deterministically generated keys do not require to be stored, because they can be generated *on the spot* – with possible usability caveat of needing the password or at least the threshold number of factors to re-generate the key. Similarly, for DKGs, depending on the particular scheme and cryptographic operation, at least the threshold number of parties might need to be online. However, DKGs enjoy an important benefit over MFKDF: the key never exists in *a complete form* at a single location. Therefore, compromising at least the threshold number of parties is required.

(Master) Key generation. When generating the key (i.e. master key), the main driver is the asymmetric scheme (i.e. crypto scheme) within which a key is going to be used. In the context of digital signature, the examples of common schemes are RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman) [23, 25] and ECDSA (Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm) [15]. The signature schemes differ by the key and signature size, computational efficiency and security assumptions.

The public part of the master key can be registered by the appropriate Certification Authority. The certification cryptographically binds several parameters, such as the public key, the qualified name of the holder and an expiration date. Either the private part of the master key or sub-keys derived from it are for signing operation by the end users. The sub-keys are either shares of the key that, when used together, create a valid signature as if the original private key was used (the original public key verifies the signature), or the sub-keys are cryptographically derived from it, and the verifying public key also needs to be derived accordingly.

(User) Key derivation. Data can be signed either directly by the master private key or by sub-keys or key shares that may be derived from it. Password-Based Key Derivation Function (PBKDF2) [19] and derivation based on the master key (e.g. BIP32 [22]) which partially contributes to the system resilience. Alternatively, Multi-Factor Key Derivation Function (e.g. MFKDF [19]) can be used aiming to improve trustlessness, portability, resilience and usability [19]. Multiparty Computation (MPC) allows the derivation of key shares based on the

³Those factors include the commonly used such as passwords, HOTP, TOTP, OOBA, HMAC-SHA1 (e.g. Yubikey) and other.

master key. MPC allows the creation of multi-signatures or threshold signatures (e.g. Schnorr signatures [20] or Shamir’s Secret Sharing [26]). Using MPC-based signatures improves recoverability [26] and, thus, resilience. It also enables multiple users to manage and use ODI while providing partial traceability and protection from privilege escalation by replacing a single ODI controller with a group of n users that have to participate collaboratively (all together, in case of N out of N group, or with a minimum threshold K out of N) to create a valid signature.

Second key derivation approach arose from the area of cryptocurrency wallets, where re-using public key used for “storing” the funds makes the corresponding private key a higher target for an attacker. The following two approaches arose to work around the problem of the key pair re-use. First, non-deterministic key derivation requires generating new key pair for each new signature (i.e. incoming transaction, in the context of cryptocurrency funds) [28]. Unfortunately, to prevent the loss of both current and future funds, all the randomly generated private keys need to be stored indefinitely. Moreover, because the keys are unrelated, the key registration process would need to be repeated for each new key. Second, Hierarchical Deterministic wallets (HD) derive the child keys from a root key pair. Example of such a key derivation (or in the academic literature called rerandomization) is Bitcoin Improvement Proposal No. 32 (BIP32) [17, 10]. The child public keys can be calculated using the parent public key and without having the corresponding private key. Also, the keys can match the hierarchical organisational structure. In the case of usage of multiple keys, the selection of the relationship between them may conditionally increase fault tolerance (e.g. HD wallet may tolerate leakage of some keys [13]), and thus, resilience. Some schemes of HD wallets may prevent the privilege escalation and ensure unforgeability [10, 9, 13]. Meanwhile, HD wallet aim to prevent linkability of both the keys and the signatures [9, 10], which in turn may negate trustlessness. However, an external auditor can still link the public keys and signatures if given the proper derivation path. Finally, the set-up of deterministic wallets may improve recoverability [13] thanks to the structure of keys. Unfortunately, the deterministically derived keys must be derived also on the side of the verifier of the signature, and therefore are not backwards compatible.

Key distribution. The key distribution phase defines the point of control over the ODI’s keys and how the keys are delivered to the controller. The point of control over the identity is driven by the level of custody over the keys. Non-custodial (i.e. self-custodial) approach [16] enables more control, but more overhead, as the identity owner is also the holder and controller, thus responsible for securing the keys. An opposite approach is full outsourcing of the control (i.e. custody) [19], which removes operational overhead from the ODI owner, but also the control. The full ODI custody directly conflicts with the zero trust concept as it assumes the trust to a third party who manages keys and conducts operations on behalf of the organisation. Both approaches

do not address trustlessness, resilience or protection from privilege escalation, and enable conditional multiple users by means of internal organisational access control.

Another approach for defining a point of control is partial custody, which is based on the decentralised control and storage of keys either for signing and/or for recovery. This means that the system can operate with a reduced reliance on trust, as cryptographic keys are distributed, which eliminates a single point of failure or malicious manipulation to compromise the security of the system. Consequently, partial custody can substantially bolster the system’s overall security posture, mitigating the risks associated with centralised control of keys. This allows to bring trustlessness, improve recoverability and resilience, support traceability, and may conditionally allow multiple user and prevention from privilege escalation.

2.2 Operational key phase

Key storage. The cryptographic keys used for encryption or signing are stored on tokens that also generate, protect and manage them. The token can be a software application installed on a general-purpose device, e.g. the one that requests the signature, or a full-fledged external device such as a Hardware Security Module (HSM). The dedicated device can be a USB token, a smart card (e.g. JavaCard) or a trusted platform module built into an end-consumer device. For example, JavaCard is a pocket-sized computing device, which can run applets for configuring the keys usage functions (e.g. IsoApplet [1], OpenFIPS201 [2]). Another device relevant for storing keys is a hardware wallet. The form of a token affects ODI’s portability and usability. Both forms of a token and wallet affect ODI’s portability as they define how users can access the keys. If the hierarchical deterministic key derivation is used, lost child keys can be recovered from the master key pair.

Key usage (Signing and Verification). This step is not a part of the key management lifecycle [8] but is conducted during the operational phase. On the level of single signer and verifier, the digital signature scheme defines the algorithms of signing and verification. RSA (Rivest-Shamir-Adleman) and ECDSA (Elliptic Curve Digital Signature Algorithm) are the most used algorithms [10, 9] while lattice-based (e.g. CRYSTALS-Dilithium [12]) and hash-based signature schemes (e.g. SPHINCS+) are more recent quantum-resistant [4]. A signature scheme defines the level of the signature unforgeability and affects the level of usability and traceability. Additionally, the proposed in [27] two-tier signature claims to improve the unforgeability and prevent linkability of the signature of single users [27, 5]. In the case of multiple signers, the set-up of the signers group and the rules of the final group signature creation [11] can be done using mechanisms such as Schnorr multi-signature (e.g. MuSig [20, 21] and threshold Shamir’s Secret Sharing signature [26]). Threshold signature helps to hide the identities of exact signers who participate in the signature creation from the verifier as the final group signature does not contain details about whether it

was created by one signer or multiple. On the other hand, the group set-up may enforce mandatory participation of the defined entities in the group signature. Thus, the ODI owner can trace back to some extent who of the shareholders participated in the signature creation. From the point of the verifier there can be differences whether a threshold variant of the signature scheme is verifiable without any changes or not.

Key back up and Recovery For data recovery in case of private key loss, an identity holder should back up the private key somewhere else than the storage for regular key usage. Such backup storage can be an additional HSM, a trusted execution environment (TEE) for key backup [26] or a third-party custodianship of the keys. The latter carries the risks of identity theft through privilege escalation [26]. For enhanced security, an identity holder may employ secure Multi-party Computation (MPC) and threshold secret sharing – distributing key shares among multiple custodians to backup the private key. Later, a minimum number of custodians must provide their key shares to the identity holder to recover the backed-up key [26].

3 Results

To sum up, through the literature review, we have identified a number of cryptographic and non-cryptographic mechanisms which help to secure key materials or signatures used on behalf of the organisational digital identity. Figure 2 provides the mapping of system properties (targeted in X-Road scenario) which can be achieved by employing the reviewed key management mechanisms. The mapping highlights the key phase and the category of mechanisms, the implementation of which primarily affects the respective system characteristics. An empty cell in Figure 2 means that there is no direct effect or we lack evidence (in the form of mechanisms in our review) which would confirm the effect.

One finding from the literature comes from the fact that we conducted the review considering the centrally issued and certified organisational digital identity with PKI certificates. However, we found that the same mechanism and properties are also used for identity management in the decentralised identities (issued through blockchain-based IdM system) [14, 17, 26, 4]. Moreover, some blockchain-based data exchange systems have internal mechanisms which enable such security properties as unlinkability of identities and decentralisation [4]. Additionally, distributed ledger-based IdM systems (including self-sovereign identities) aim to enable trustlessness by removing a single point of identity issuance [7, 3]. Nevertheless, traditional IdM systems are still the primary source of identities, and, moreover, both PKI-based traditional and blockchain-based IdM systems rely on the PKI. Thus, key management is still the task to be done.

Characteristic	X-Road		Pre operational phase			Operational phase			Recovery
	current state	targeted state	Related targeted goals	Key gener.	(User) Key derivation	Key distribution	Key storage	Key usage	
	● or ○	● or ○		crypto schemes	Factors for key deriv. * MPC_sign. *	Point of control	Token form * Wallet form * Tokens relationship *	Sign. & verif. algorithm	
Fault Tolerance	●	● or ○			±		±		
Availability	○	○				±			
Unforgeability	●	●					±	±	
Linkability	●	●					±	±	
Recoverability	○	○ or ●			±				±
Decentralisation	○	● or ○	G1			±			
Trustlessness	○	●	G1			±			
Portability	○	○	G1					±	
Resilience	○	○			±				
Multiple user	○	○	G1, G2		±				
Traceability	○	○	G2		±				
Usability	●	○						±	
Prevention from privilege escalation	○	○	G3		±				
Legend:	<p>● characteristic is achieved</p> <p>○ characteristic is partially achieved</p> <p>○ the mechanism in the phase may affect the characteristic</p> <p>● characteristic is achieved under conditions</p> <p>○ characteristic is not achieved or prevented</p> <p>* optional mechanisms</p>								
	Characteristic change:								
	Improved								
	downgraded								
	not changed								

Figure 2: Mapping of system properties and mechanisms categories (marked in red are mechanisms which affect the targeted system properties in X-Road)

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